

Wearing gloves when eviscerating animals protects hunters from hepatitis E

BfR Information No 047/2015, 14 December 2015

Wild boars can carry the hepatitis E virus (HEV). For hunters, direct contact with wild boars during field dressing for producing game meat therefore poses an increased infection risk. A study coordinated by the Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) and conducted in close cooperation with the competent authorities of an administrative district, the Friedrich-Loeffler-Institute, and the Robert Koch-Institute investigated the distribution of HEV and HEV-specific antibodies in hunters of that administrative district and also in wild boars within the relevant hunting territories. In addition, the study succeeded in identifying the risk and protective factors of HEV transmission to hunters. Analysis of the collected data showed that the detection rate for HEV-specific antibodies for hunters who often wear gloves when eviscerating animals is 88% lower than for those hunters who disembowelled hunted game without gloves. This means that wearing gloves when eviscerating and carving up wild boars is an effective protection measure to prevent transmission of HEV.

The full version of this BfR Information is available in German on

<http://vm-webextern-m.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/tragen-von-handschuhen-beim-ausweiden-schuetzt-jaeger-vor-hepatitis-e.pdf>